

REPORT:

*A1.1.4: Generic specification list for
comparison of flow control components*

Work package 1

This report was written as part of activity 1.1.4 from the EMPIR Establishing Metrology Standards in Microfluidic Devices (MFMET) project. The three-year European project commenced on 1st June 2021 and focused on providing a generic methodology of accurate measurement of a particular quantity in a microfluidic device by utilising standardised methods and reference documents, e.g. VIM & GUM. For more details about this project, please visit www.mfmet.eu

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1. Scope

This document provides a generic specifications list with key parameters (e.g. micro/nano/femtolitre flow rates, fluid properties, dead micro-volumes) to enable the comparison of flow control components, based on A1.1.1 - A1.1.3 reports, and end-user advisory board.

Activity number	Activity description	Partners (Lead in bold)
A1.1.4 M14	Using input from A1.1.1-A1.1.3 and the End-user Advisory Board (A5.1.1), CETIAT, DTI, INESC MN, HSG-IMIT and BHT will define a generic specifications list with key parameters (e.g. micro/nano/femtolitre flow rates, fluid properties, dead micro-volumes) to enable the comparison of flow control components. Using the specifications list, CETIAT, DTI, INESC MN, HSG-IMIT and BHT will then perform a comparison of flow control components. The results of the comparison will clarify in detail which types of components will be selected in order to fabricate/use relevant microfluidic flow control components depending on the function and application, to be used in A1.2.3, A2.2.3 and A2.3.3.	CETIAT , DTI, INESC MN, HSG-IMIT, BHT

2. Introduction

Several microfluidic flow control components are available on the market. The relevant technical information from the datasheet will enable end-users to compare the performance of the microfluidic flow control components and to choose the best-fitted for their application. Without a standardized datasheet, the comparison of the performance of different microfluidic flow control component is often not possible due to the lack of similar information or divergent definitions of similar performance characteristics.

The following groups of characteristics are defined, described and explained with examples where it is appropriate:

- Technology Characteristics
- General working conditions
- Electronical Characteristics
- Mechanical Characteristics
- Flow Characteristics

For the purposes of this document, the terms and definitions given in ISO 10991 and JCGM 200:2012 apply.

- International Organization for Standardization. ISO, ISO/DIS 10991 Microfluidics — Vocabulary; ISO: Geneva, Switzerland (<https://www.iso.org/standard/82146.html>)
- VIM3: JCGM 200, International Vocabulary of Metrology – Basic and General Concepts and Associated Terms (VIM 3rd edition), BIPM, 2012 (<https://www.bipm.org/en/publications/guides/vim.html>)

ISO and IEC maintain terminological databases for use in standardization at the following addresses:

- IEC Electropedia: available at <http://www.electropedia.org/>
- ISO Online browsing platform: available at <https://www.iso.org/obp>

3. Technology Characteristics

3.1. Actuation Type

The actuation type of a given flow control component corresponds to the main energy source which is used to start and/or put into operation the component. Examples are electrical, pneumatic, or mechanical (hand-driven or requesting an external mechanical actuator). In any case, the minimum and maximum intensity levels of the characteristics of the required energy should be provided in the datasheet examples are "4 V to 10 V DC", or "0.2 to 2 bar", along with the required stability and/or periodicity.

3.2. Dead Volume

Portion of the internal volume of a system that is not part of a continuous flow-path. In this context dead signifies unmoving, stagnant, or un-swept. Expressed in volume quantities such as mm³ or microliter [ISO 10991 definition 5.1.4].

3.3. Requirement of additional consumables

Any requirement for additional consumables, necessary for the correct operation of the component, should be specified, along with their expected lifetime, dimensions, materials, etc. Examples are removable syringes for syringe pumps, peristaltic pump main tubing, fittings and connectors, gaskets, membranes, etc.

3.4. Operational lifetime

Expected duration for which the component is operating under the nominal specifications.

3.5. Reusability

Indication to the reusability of the component should be given, along with the expected lifespan.

3.6. Wetted material

Information about all materials in contact with the fluid should be given in the datasheet. When appropriate, biocompatibility, compatibility with organic solvents, pH-resistance range, temperature and pressure operational ranges of all wetted materials should be provided in the datasheet.

3.7. Reversible flow

Information about the possibility of generating and/or handling a reversible flow should be given in the datasheet. If appropriate, a specific reversible flow duration tolerance should be given.

3.8. Closed loop possibility

The possibility to actuate and/or control the flow by integrating the component in a closed loop system can be given in the datasheet. Information about the required piloting signal(s) (electrical, pneumatic) and their operating ranges can be given. Additional information about the sensor(s) used for feedback control can be included.

4. General working conditions

4.1. Maximum pressure delivered

The maximum pressure delivered at the outlet of the component should be given in the datasheet. If appropriate, a maximum pressure per operational and/or consumable-specific condition of use should be specified in the datasheet. Example: 4 bar maximum for a 1 ml plastic syringe.

4.2. Ability to work in an incubator

The ability to work in an incubator can be specified in the datasheet. When needed, restriction to the operational performances (flow rate range, etc.) can be described.

4.3. Self-priming

If the component has the ability to self-prime its internal volume, the self-priming procedure should be given in the datasheet.

4.4. Self-heating

The level of self-heating should be given in terms of unit of temperature per operational level (flow rate, outlet pressure) and for a given fluid (examples: pure water, air, etc.).

4.5. Sound level

The sound level, in dB, should be given in the datasheet. The sound level should be given for the nominal operating condition and/or for the maximum operating condition. Alternatively, the sound level range (example: 35 dB to 40 dB) can be given for a specified operating range.

4.6. Certifications

Description of the reference document or legislation applied to the certification of the product should be included in the datasheet.

4.7. Back pressure

The maximum level of back-pressure for which the component remains within its operational conditions (flow rate range, accuracy), should be specified in the datasheet.

5. Electronical Characteristics

5.1. Power supply

The required power supply characteristics should be provided in the datasheet along with the required stability and/or periodicity, such as "4 V to 10V DC".

5.2. Electromagnetic compatibility

The ability of equipment or a system to function satisfactorily in its electromagnetic environment without introducing intolerable electromagnetic disturbances to anything in that environment (IEV 161-01-07)

NOTE: Electromagnetic compatibility (compliance) level should be quantified in the datasheet. If appropriate, agreement to a specific electromagnetic compliance standard or directive should be described in the datasheet.

6. Mechanical Characteristics

6.1. Internal volume

Maximal total available volume comprised within a fluidic component, device or system under normal atmospheric pressure; this is the total of dead volume and swept volume. Expressed in volume quantities such as mm³ or microliter [ISO 10991 definition 5.1.10].

6.2. Dimension – Size

The external dimensions of the component should be provided in the datasheet, either with the adequate values in dimensional unit, or illustrated in a technical drawing. For each component's dimension, tolerances can be provided.

6.3. Weight

The unloaded total weight of the component should be provided in the datasheet. When used with necessary accessories or consumables (syringes, tubing, etc), the manufacturer should describe in the datasheet if the indicated weight is given for a pump with or without its consumables/accessories.

6.4. Working pressure

The operating working pressure of the component shall be given in pressure unit, for specified operating conditions and a specified fluid.

6.5. Integration level

The integration possibilities/level can be described in the datasheet, for example by listing compatible components and/or devices, or examples of integration in other systems.

6.6. Output/Input connector and accessories type

The types of required of compatible input and/or output connectors and accessories should be specified in the datasheet. Examples are Luer, Luer-lock, clamps, etc.

7. Flow Characteristics

7.1. Standard deviation (stability)

The stability of the flow rate generated by the component should be expressed in the datasheet by a quantified value of its standard deviation. The standard deviation can either be expressed in flow units, by a single value or a range of values, or by a percentage of the maximum or nominal flow.

7.2. Response time

Interval of time between the set point step change the moment the flow (or generated pressure) has increased x% of its intended rise or x% of its intended fall. Typically x=90. Expressed in time units [ISO 10991 definition 5.1.17]

7.3. Flow accuracy

Closeness of agreement between a measured quantity value and a true quantity value of a measurand [JCGM 200:2012 entry 2.15].

For a flow control component, the flow accuracy should be given for specified operating conditions and for a specified fluid.

7.4. Open state fluidic resistance

For peristaltic and diaphragm/membrane pump, the open state (i.e of the pump itself) fluidic resistance should be given in pressure over flow rate units.

7.5. Flow rate range and limits

The flow rate range and limits should be given for specified operating conditions and for a specified fluid.

8. Key parameters

Based on the previous chapters characteristics, MFMET consortium & end-users experience, and A1.1.1-A.1.3 outcomes (described in their respective reports), MFMET selected the following key parameters to be used to compare flow control components:

- Flow characteristics
 - Range
 - Stability
 - Unit

- Mechanical characteristics
 - Pressure
 - Range
 - Unit
 - Connections
 - Type
 - Size